

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B267
Date: 07 Feb 2007
Take Off: 10:34:36
Landing: 15:48:39
Flight Time: 5h14m03

Campaign: VISURB

Operating Area: East & South coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	MARSS / FWVS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
8	ARIES	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
9	SWS	Martyn Glew	Met Office
10	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
11	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Pollard	Met Office
12	AMS	Jonny Crosier	University of Manchester
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Flight Track:

B267 Track 07-FEB-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b267

Date: 07 February 2007

Project: VISURB

Location: E and S coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
091428		Start-Up	0.64 kft	104	52'04.35N, 0'37.48W
094312		INU	0.64 kft	104	To Navigate
103436		T/O	1.5 kft	030	Cranfield
104039		ASPs	8.9 kft	022	Open
104652		Videos	11.0 kft	051	FFC & UFC
105626	110241	Profile	11.1 - 5.0 kft	325	1
110424	110842	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.87 kft	131	int @1000',end 500'
110842	111606	Run 1.1	0.90 - 1.1 kft	131	500'
111640	112105	Run 1.1	1.4 - 1.3 kft	147	To 1k' avoid cloud
111857		Heimann	1.4 kft	166	Cal
112217	123700	Run 1.1	0.85 - 0.89 kft	193	500',Q1001 500fpm
112302		Heimann	0.86 kft	188	Cal
113127		Event	0.88 kft	182	@ WP 41
114505		Event	0.86 kft	212	@ WP 42
115652		Event	0.84 kft	250	@ WP 43
121130		Event	0.80 kft	273	@ WP 44, Q1003
122608		Event	0.87 kft	246	@ WP 45
122623		Video	0.87 kft	273	Change Tapes
123701	123800	Profile 2	0.89 - 1.7 kft	269	1000fpm from 1k'
123806	124146	Profile 2	1.8 - 5.0 kft	273	
124806	125427	Profile 3	7.0 - 1.4 kft	087	To 1k', Q1002
125428	131128	Run 2	1.4 kft	091	1000'
125821		Event	1.4 kft	085	@ WP 45
131128	131332	Profile 4	1.4 - 0.36 kft	046	1k' - 50'
131332	131721	Profile 5	0.36 - 3.3 kft	047	50' - 3k'
131516		Event	1.4 kft	076	Abeam WP 44
132011	132415	Profile 6	3.3 - 0.36 kft	236	3k' - 50', Q1002
132415	132552	Profile 7	0.36 - 1.3 kft	240	50' - 1k'
132734	140816	Run 3	1.4 - 1.3 kft	088	1k'
133125		Event	1.3 kft	049	WP 44
134829		Event	1.3 kft	073	@ WP 43
135022		Event	1.3 kft	060	Q1001
135833		Videos	1.3 kft	056	Change Tapes
140153		Event	1.3 kft	043	@ WP 42
140816	141033	Profile 8	1.3 - 0.37 kft	010	1k' - 50'
141033	141340	Profile 9	0.37 - 2.8 kft	014	50' - 2.5k'
141550	141936	Profile 10	2.8 - 0.38 kft	228	2.5k - 50'
141936	142045	Profile 11	0.38 - 1.3 kft	243	50' - 1k'
142553	144037	Run 4	1.4 - 1.3 kft	018	1k'
143027		Event	1.3 kft	358	@ WP 41
144224	144445	Profile 12	1.4 - 0.40 kft	192	1k' - 50'
144446	144658	Profile 13	0.40 - 1.9 kft	200	50' - 1.5k'
144711	144840	Profile 14	2.0 - 1.4 kft	184	1.5k' - 1k'
145009	151223	Run 5	1.4 kft	007	1k'
150213		Event	1.4 kft	337	Turn 7nm before WP40
151358	151710	Profile 15	2.4 - 0.40 kft	079	2k' - 50'
151711	152234	Profile 16	0.40 - 5.0 kft	100	50' - FL50
153507		Videos	12.0 kft	248	End of Tapes
153614		ASPs	12.0 kft	248	Closed
154839		Land	0.69 kft	355	Cranfield
155252		Shutdown	0.68 kft	304	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

FAAM Sortie Brief

VISURB UK. Assessment of aerosol properties related to visibility

Flight No: B267

Date: 7th February 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of aerosol properties and their effect on radiation.

Location:

Off the east and south coast of the UK.

Weather:

High loadings of atmospheric aerosols, preferred cloud-free but not essential.

Special requirements:

Check the mesoscale model forecast for the position of aerosol plumes before flying.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:30Z.
2. Transit to AMPEP point 87 at FL110 [20mins, T=20mins]
3. Perform a broke profile descent at 1000ft/minute to 500ft to finish back at point 87 [10mins, T=30mins].
4. Perform a long SLR at 500ft heading southwards around the coast. [100mins, T=130mins].
5. Where concentrations of atmospheric aerosols are high, mark point Xray and break the SLR, and perform three additional reciprocal runs of 5 mins duration at 1000ft, 2500ft, and 5000ft [20mins, T=150mins].
6. Reposition the aircraft to point Xray at 500ft [5mins, T=155mins]
7. Continue the 500ft run around the coast as far as point 46 [Tmax=155 mins].
8. Make reciprocal turn and return along the same track at 500ft heading east and following AMPEP points [100 mins, T=255 mins].
9. Carry out a profile at some point during the return leg. Aim to do this within a region of high aerosol concentration (point "Xray"). This manoeuvre would consist of a descent to 50ft and a profile ascent to FL050. Make a reciprocal turn before a profile descent to 500ft, then reposition to re-commence the SLR from the position where the SLR had been interrupted to make the profiles [15mins, T=270mins].
10. Continue the SLR at 500ft round the coast heading back towards point 87 [complete by T=270 mins].
11. Transit back to Cranfield [30mins, T = 300mins]
12. Land Cranfield.

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet (S.R. Osborne)

B267

7th February 2007

Summary of the weather conditions

Low pressure vortex in the North Sea, showery conditions, some fairly close to the East Anglian coast. More stable conditions over the country, cold frosty start (-7degC at Cranfield). Fairly clear skies over land; some low level cloud and cirrus over sea areas such as the English Channel. Airflow- very gentle NW'ly, advecting trapped low-level pollution over southern North Sea and English Channel.

Summary of the flight

A successful sortie was carried out as part of the VISURB campaign to measure aerosol properties of UK (industrial-type) pollution. A pollution monitoring flight track was performed based on some of the AMPEP fixed way points. Our start point was 87 (Blakeney Point, Norfolk). A profile descent was made from FL110, starting at pt 87 and breaking the profile at FL050 over the sea heading NW, to finish heading SE towards pt 40 (meant to be twds 87, but we were losing time on the NOTAM booking). There was shallow cu in this area, tops ~1300ft, with pollution trapped beneath. Run 1 was at 500ft heading clockwise around the coast. Due to poor visibility (stratus?), we had to rise to 1000ft for ~5 mins before descending back to 500ft. Cloud conditions were variable during Run 1, with some limited radiation work possible early on. Much of the run within the London plume was below 7/8 Ci (which seemed to be predominantly contrail-induced). In the heaviest loadings, PCASP concs were ~3000/cc (rough estimate). There was lots of small-ish scale structure in the aerosol properties, presumably plumes from coastal sources (and ships!) adding to the general polluted background. The end of Run 1 was called before pt 47 was reached (the planned end pt), due to very low aerosol loadings; concs dropped off around pt 45. The AMS showed predominantly ammonium nitrate within the pollution, with sulphate dominating in the cleaner conditions west of pt 45.

A profile was made to FL050 as a comfort break, turning and starting the return leg at 1000 ft above the sea surface, closer to the pollution tops, initially below broken cu. This anti-clockwise leg was broken three times to carry out a profile descent and ascent from 50ft to just above the pollution to monitor the vertical structure. The top of the pollution was lower around the east coast (~1300ft) than the south coast (~2000ft). For much of the run we were skimming just in the pollution top. A time series of the neph scattering shows a different structure of the pollution at 1000ft compared to 500ft e.g. peak values were higher at 500ft (neph green ~ $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in London plume). Small cu (cu humulis) were often forming on top of the pollution, seeded with pollution CCN! The anti-clockwise leg was probably better on the whole for the radiation work (e.g. SWS). The final profile descent showed the pollution tops at ~680ft (!), but this was right on the Norfolk coast.

Comparison of the Met Office aerosol model with observations will be interesting on this day- to see if the model captured the low-level capping of the pollution at the correct (variable) height as well as the usual visibility parameter variation with height and spatial cover.

Instruments

Neph 1 and neph 2 were both operated (both 'dry'); I was expecting neph1 to be mostly U/S based on previous flights. But no ! Both nephs appeared to work ok throughout the whole flight. It will be interesting to compare the two datasets.

PCASP1 (old one)- bin 1 noise only.

PCASP2 (new one) – big problems; noise all over the place (bins 1,2,3,4 at least); data rubbish.

TWC- first flight after Exeter fix; seemingly working fine.

AMS- no GRIMM, but otherwise fine.

CVI- not operated.

SHIMS/SWS- worked fine.

Mission Scientist's Log

S. R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.267**.....

Date **07/02/07**.....

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INSTR:

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	No CVI (no operator - forgot!)				PSAP → recording to hypertherm. unit on PC
	PCASP1 etc. (apart from bin)				Neph1 → SURFACE
	PCASP2 switched on but effectively off				Neph2 → Labview on PC.
	Neph1	B → G → R		looks fine	pre-flight.
	zeros carried out on both nephs successfully				
1035	climb.				cancel. Ci near SW → Piconettes
					can see polluted BL all around.
					→ Pollution seem to be trapped below 2500ft
					low thin ST or fog v. low in places.
1051		FL100			TRANSIT. ST/CI overland by some stairs maybe? bubbles can cover sea cloud. clear skies above.
1055					overcast 2-3/8 small cu below.
105624	P1 ↓	FL110	325	53° 0' N 0° 54' E	start profile descent. 1000 ft/min. fairly clear of cloud above now. (small patch) winds look like ~280° from water.
		FL085			
110239	P1 →	FL050	000	53° 18' N 0° 36' E	Interrupt descent.
110423	P1 ↓	FL050	131	53° 0' N 1° 42' E	re-start descent + winds point to (to recover some time - better!) ENC reading zero - better?
					→ High flow mode. clear - now (1.3 VA) hollow Cu. visibility!!
110745		1000'			re-Interrupt down 1300'
110754	P1 ↓	1000'			re-start descent.
110840	R1	500'	131	53° 06' N 1° 6' E	End profile / Start run. Neph1 B-G-R de!

0.55
TST in 50 ft 200' w-4

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.267**

 Date **07/02/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	R1				Skimming below. SIMAN an.
					CNC ~ 5000/cc. agreeing with AMS. c/c
					PCASP ~ 400/cc (rust estimate)
111300					small plume. PCASP ~ 900/cc.
					Nth NO ₂ : AMS predominant
111545					low st. Hit Ea. Poor vis, climbing up
111640	R1	1000'			steadily ascend (SLR) to 1000'
					crystal clear above.
111935	R1	1000'	187		Cones dropping off now
112105	R1 ↓	500' ↓			descend back. 600' → hit plume again
112205	R1	500'			SLR again.
112530					7/8 for Ci ahead. clear at low st now.
					good vis, MIS.
					Next working fire!! (so far)
					v. plumes etc.
112930					low st ahead! vis poorer for a short while.
					(SS 2-3).
113125	R1.	500'			Pt. 41. now. (gentle visit here).
					skipping into Felixstone area here.
					pred. NO ₂ , occasional SO ₂
1136					PCASP 3000/cc CNC ~ 8000/cc.
114100					highest cones now.
					(pts of contrast-induced Ci above
114457	R1	500'			point 42 now. 7/8!!
					can see dark plume to the left,
					overhead & splitting out.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.267**

 Date **07/02/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115039	R1	500'			On field out to the left.
1153					* occasional drop-outs - o.d. failure * in data happened. Three rows.
115645	R1	500'			Point 43 now. Steady eyes → no major plumes. Abandon search of suns.
115846	R1	500'			2/8 Ci (contrails) above.
1205	R1	500'			Minor plumes here } Comes left at 1139 red droppings off, but one steady. } things, but narrow plume. 7/8 Ci above
1208	R1	500'			True gases grades. visible left 15 min
121140	R1	500'			Point 46 now; Edge of night
121700					3/8 visible in above now; Ci disappearing. [Behind schedule] No time to X-ray!!
122200	R1	500'			SHS PLU ME SIBITCE. hill on, nothing on road. went through a few plumes, actually
122430	R1	500'	219	50°0'N 104°4'W	4/8 above Ci, joined back to them (1000ft?) free of Ci above (I think). No pl droppings low now.
122550	R1	500'			point 45 now NO3 → 260y on AMS
123654	R1	2500'	268	49°50'N 3°0'W	different region here. End Run + start ascent.
123900					2800' → bases of cloud, lit cloud.
		2050			End profile for comcast (BROOKS)
1252					descending to 1000ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

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 Date **07/02/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125426	P3 / R2	1000'	090	50° 0' N 2° 18' W	End profile & start SLR.
					↖
1257	R2	1000'	090		Just ↓ elevated $\sigma_p \sim 35 \times 10^{-6}$ PCASP in 200/ce. Steady signals.
125820	R2	1000'			point 45 now (turn left). 4/8 Cu / Scm above.
130500	R2	1000'			Lower visibility now - VPS reducing - NOx - 29 ppbv. Can see dark layer ahead. No Cu now - cloud free !!
131128	R2 / P4 ↓	1000	046	50° 30' N 1° 12' W	Start profile descent / end SLR
131331	P4 ↓	50'	047	50° 36' N 1° 6' W	End descent / start ascent
1317 21	P5	3000'	089		End ascent, turn about turn.
132011	P6 ↓	3000'	235	50° 36' N 0° 48' W	Start profile descent back into
13240 13	P6 → P7 V7	50'	241	50° 30' N 1° 6' W	End descent / start ascent back to 1000'
132551	P7	1000'	244	50° 30' N 1° 18' W	End profile ascent mid-pollution layer clear skies above.
132733	R3	1000'	087	50° 30' N 1° 12' W	Start run in pollution
133120	R3	1000'			point 44 now.
133730					PCASP visible 200 → 1200/ce.
134010	R3	1000'			light Cu nothing in top of pollution to the left. O ₃ = 20 - 25 ppbv.
134755	R3	1000'			Below tr. Cu now.
134920					point 43 now.
1350					wiggles for traffic.
1353	R3	1000'			Distinct top to the brown pollution

1040 200 point 42 Dimer marks
: comes spiking (ship plumes?) to the left.

Mission Scientist's Log

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 Date **07/02/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140815	R3 / P8	1000' ↓	010	51°24' 1°36'	End run / start descent.
141032	P8/P9	50' ↓	014	51°30' 1°36'	Descent / ascent in good pollution.
		~1800'			Top of pollution haze. Clear directly above.
141337	P9	2500'	016	51°42' 1°42'	in clear air. Right turn.
					some Ci further afield near Sun.
141549	P10 ↓	2500' ↓	228	51°36' 1°48'	Start profile descent.
	P10 ↓	~1350'			Hit top of haze.
141935	P10/P11	50' ↓	242	51°30' 1°30'	End descent / start ascent to 1200ft.
142044	P11	1000'	236	51°30' 1°24'E	End profile ascent in pollution.
					Contrail-induced Ci above in turn.
	P14	1000'			Start SLR (anti-clockwise and coast)
					(comes a little jumpy, but overall steady.)
143016	P14	1000'	358	51°48' 1°42'	point 41 reached.
					clear skies above now - good for photo.
143600		1000'			CRASP ~ 10000e, but has been higher
					streaming down at haze here (~2500' level).
143700					almost come out tops of
144036	P14	1000'	000	52°24' 1°48'	End SLR, right turn
144223	P12 ↓	1000' ↓	171	52°24' 1°48'	Start profile descent into haze.
		500'			v. white appearance into Sun!
					higher cones now.
144443	P12/P13	50' ↓	179	52°18'N 1°48'E	End profile descent.
		1600'			out of haze
144655	P13 ↑	1500'	185	52°6' 1°42'	End ascent - above tops
144710	P14 ↓	1500'			Start descent back into it!!

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...267**

Date

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144839	P14 →	1000'	4		End descent, turn back onto track
145009	R5	1000'	006°	52°0'N 104°8'W	Start SLR northwards down slope above. tr. Cu to right resting in p. m. h. i.
~1452					deeper Cu on the nose - quite a distance ahead.
145800	R5	1000'	354		skimming top shell - rept varying 10 → 60 x 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻¹
~1501	R5	1000'			Cu up ahead: thicker cloud. tr. Cu skimming past us now also. clear of Ci above.
~1503	R5	1000'			cutting corner (pt 40) to avoid Cu. Some good aerosol hits a rept.
~150930	R5	1000'			just about overhead the beach!
151225	R5	1000'	288	52°05'N 104°E	End SLR! ^{just} in. tops of p. m. h. i. Clear of Ci good for radiance. ← left turn over land
151358	P15 ↓	2000' ↓	079	52°54' 106'	Start profile descent right on coast! above p. m. h. i. SL. → profile begins coast tightly. p. m. h. i. tops → v. low nearer land.
151708	P15 ↓ P16	50' ^1600'	101	52°42' 104'	End descent / Start ascent. top of p. m. h. i. → higher again. start clear above
152233	P16	5000'	123	52°42' 104'	End profile climb - <u>END SCIENCE</u>

PARLQKD MS2

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.267**

Date **7/2/7**

Page **1** of **3**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:35:26	T/O				Into mainly clear skies some haze and plumes trapped by inversion.
10:48:40		FL110	53		8 crossing coast into Wash, some low level cloud on coast & ahead in N. sea. Clear at high level.
10:56:26	P1 ↓	FL110	323		Some v. thin and set Cu over sea at low level
10:58					Low lev del thinning, residual haze with wave like structure to W.
11:02:41		FL50			Interrupt and turn S. back to pt 87
11:04:24		"			Recommence, heading for Pt 40 to get back on schedule.
					CPC reading 0 of 400 on AMS
		2hft			level w/ cloud.
11:07		1hft			500ft/min. ↓ fixed by switching to hi flow mode
11:08:08	R1.1	500ft			Below bases of set Cu
					No aerosol visible out of window
11:13					Sharp rise in NO ₂ & OHMS
11:14					AMS: Ammonium Nitrate
11:16:40		1000ft			up to 1000ft to avoid cloud.
11:22:17					Back down to 500ft, clear skies
11:24:					Some aerosol haze to Left (E)
11:32:40					Coming under Ci
11:46					Clear around, Ci do not threaten
12:06					Conditions pretty much unchanged

PERLADAN MS2 Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 267**.....

Date **7/2/7**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:36	R1	500ft			End
"	R2				Start to 50
12:39		2800ft			into old base
12:41:46	R2	500ft			
12:54:29	R2	1000ft			
13:11:29	R2 / R4	1000ft			down to 50ft
13:13:32	R4 / R5	50ft			up to top of pollutants
13:16					Very polluted to N.
13:17		2800ft			coming out of pollutants (NO ₂ , Neph CMC
13:17:24	R5	3000ft			cut, backtracking to get back to start
13:20:11	R6	"			to 50ft on recip
		2000ft			entering pollutants
13:24:15	R6 / R7	50ft			to 1000ft
13:25:52	R7	1000ft			Turning back onto Anti-clock circuit
13:27:34	R3	"			
13:58					Neph & NO ₂ dropping CNC inc.
14:05					couple of NO _x peaks, Neph break up
14:08:10	R5 / R8	1000ft			to 50ft
14:10:33	R8 / R9	50ft			Clear down, Hazy
14:12:50		2kft			Neph, CNC plummeting
14:13:40	R9	2.5kft			end turning round to do it again

Pollard, MS2

Mission Scientist's LogFlight No **B.267**.....Date **7/2/7**.....Page **3** of **3**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:15:50	P10	2.5 hft	Sish		CWC Nax & Nepk stabilizing at top
14:17		1.8 hft			CWC up
14:17:30		1.6 hft			Nepk up
		1.3 hft			Nax up
14:19:36	P10 / P11	50ft			upto 100ft, good Nax plume
14:20:45	P11	1000ft			
	R4	1000ft			
14:40:37	R4	1000ft			end of run, turning, reciprocal to dip down and take a lead
14:42:24	P12	1000ft			to 50ft
		500ft			Pollut ² up
14:44:46	P12 / P13	50ft			
		1500ft			Pollut ² bottomed out
14:47:11	P13 / P14	1500ft			
14:48:40	P14	1000ft			turning back out onto track
14:50:09	R15	"			in pollut ² ?
14:55					Pollut ² indicators all low dropped,
14:58					" peak.
15:07					some sub Cu about, turning early to avoid
15:12:23	R5				end
15:13:58	P15	2000ft			Sig more pollut ² at 500ft & below
15:17:11	P15 / P16	50ft			
15:22:34	P16	FL50			

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B267** Date **07/02/2007** Operat or(s) **M. OLEW** log page **1** of **1**

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				
ALL OK PRE TAKE OFF. OPTICS CLEANED. SHUTTERS WORKING. ONLY HAVE VIS MODULES FITTED RE INPERATURE									
1057	R1	FL110	+6°	350	—		✓		
				200				✓	
				1000					✓
1059	PREEZE	TEMP			+1°C				
11090	R1	500'	+6°	250			✓		
				200				✓	
				1000					✓
1113	R1	500'	+6°	200		Broken column above sun saturating in this			
				500		FREEZE PLG°C			
1115	R1	500'	+6°	500					✓
1120	R1	1000'	+6°	200		Above 8/8 sc.			
1122	R1	500'	+6°	500		over clear sea.			✓
						SWS NOT MOVED FROM +6			
1134						SUN BEHIND CLOUDS.			
1220						currus gone scattered in the saturating sun			
12370	R1 END	500'	+6°	200		Scattered in	✓		
				200				✓	
				500					✓
12542	R2	1000'	+6°	200		cu/sc above	✓		
				200				✓	
				500					✓
1307						CLEAR SKIES AD OUP.			
13128	R2 END	1000'	+6°						
13273	R2	1000'	+6°	200			✓		
				200				✓	
				500					✓
1341						currus over the sun			
140816	R3 end	1000'	+6°						
141550	R10	2500'	+6°						
1421						cu above			
14250	R4	1000'	+6°	200			✓		
				200				✓	
				500					✓
144037	R4 END								
144224	R12	1000'	+6°	200			✓		
144446	R13	50'	+6°	200			✓		
145004	R5	1000'	+6°	200			✓		
				200				✓	
				500					✓
151223	R5 end	1000'	+6°	200			✓		
151358	R11	2000'	+6°	200/200/500			✓	✓	✓
151711	R16	50'	+6°	200/200/500			✓	✓	✓
152224	R11 end	5000'	+6°	200/200/500			✓	✓	✓
						END			
						CLEAR			

ARIES flight log

Flight:

page 1 of 5

Date: 7/2/2007

Operator(s): D T W E M A W

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Viswrb

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
100801	Ground	1x60	C	C	71	31	
100840	"	1x60	H	C	72	31	
104943	FL110	1x60	C	C	71	31	
105028	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
105133	"	120x1	N	C	71	31	Keyboard stopped working
110410	PS000H	1x60	C	C	71	30	Re-logged in - seems ok
110843	S00H	1x60	C	C	71	30	Run 1
110918	"	1x60	H	C	71	21	
111010	"	300x1	Z	0	71	30	Failed?
111104	"	"	"	"	70	30	Cloudy
111400	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
111437	"	"	H	C	71	31	
111527	"	300x1	Z	0	71	31	- Stopped early - changed level
111720	900H	1x60	C	C	71	31	
111754	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
111850	"	300x1	N	C	71	31	- Changed level again Heiman Cal
112210	S00H	300x1	N	C	71	31	Heiman Cal
112543	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
112625	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
112720	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
113010	"	1x60	C	C	70	31	
113048	"	"	H	C	71	31	
113200	"	300x1	Z	0	70	30	
113450	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
113533	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
113650	"	120x1	Z	0	71	30	Curves ... Failed
113826	"	120x1	Z	0	70	31	Curves
113940	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
114020	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
114154	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	Curves
114432	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B267

page 2 of 5

Date: 7/2/07

Operator(s): D. T. Idman

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B₂

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
114528	500ft	1x60	C	C	71	31	
114610	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
114700	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
114940	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
115025	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
115102	"	1x60	H	C	71	30	
115147	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
115436	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
115527	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
115607	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
115656	"	400x1	Z	0	70	31	
120028	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
120118	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
120158	"	1x60'	H	C	71	31	
120238	"	300x1	Z	0	70	30	
120523	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
120603	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
120643	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
120723	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
121003	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
121042	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
121118	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
121254	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
121535	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
121616	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
121652	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
121740	"	300x1	Z	0	70	30	
122023	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
122106	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
122141	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
122227	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	Clear Cu

ARIES flight log

Flight: B267

page 3 of 5

Date: 7/2/07

Operator(s): D. Tiddeman

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
122504	500ft	120x1	N	C	71	31	
122622	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
122658	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
122742	"	300x1	Z	O	70	31	
123033	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
123113	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
123150	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
123244	"	300x1	Z	O	70	31	
123527	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
123617	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
123654	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	- Started probe exp !
125455	1000ft	1x60	C	C	71	31	Run 2 - return leg
125537	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
125620	"	300x1	Z	O	70	31	
125903	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
125947	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
130023	"	1x60	H	C	71	30	
130100	"	300x1	Z	O	70	30	
130352	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
130433	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
130512	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
130601	"	300x1	Z	O	71	31	
130844	"	60x1	N	C	71	30	
130925	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
131001	"	1x60	H	C	71	30	
131039	"	300x1	Z	O	70	30	
132603	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	Run 3
132647	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
132749	"	300x1	Z	O	70	31	
133033	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
133115	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B267

page 4 of 5

Date: 7/2/07

Operator(s): D. TIDEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
133202	1000H	1x60	H	C	71	31	Run 3
133300	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
133545	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
133630	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
133706	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
133870	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
134112	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
134202	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
134240	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
134329	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
134840	"	60x1 1x60	C	C	71	30	
134924	"	1x60	H	C	71	30	
135017	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
135256	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
135409	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
135445	"	1x60	H	C	71	30	
135526	"	300x1	Z	0	70	30	
135837	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
135922	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
135958	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
140100	"	300x1	Z	0	70	31	
140515	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
140558	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
140640	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
142109	1000H	1x60	C	C	71	31	Run 4
142147	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
142258	"	600x1	Z	0	71	31	
142813	"	60x1	N	C	71	31	
143037	"	1x60	C	C	71	31	
143108	"	1x60	H	C	71	31	
143230	"	300x	Z	0	70	31	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	07/02/07	Flight	B267	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	WINTEX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	0920ish
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	0920ish
Initial target temperatures	Hot	270	Cold	270		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	0920
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	10:20:22	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345	Cold	272.5
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
		33.4	37.5	39.7	42.5

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	
						1020is
						h

Flight:

B267

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 15/03/2007
12:08:27**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

09/02/2007 14:04:12

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B267

Date: 07 Feb 2007

Instruments

1. HORACE – Optical disk problems after take-off. Stopped h_optic, turned disk over and restarted. Continued to have problems so stopped h_optic again, put another disk in and restarted.
2. CPC – reading zero at low level compared to AMS 400 counts. FAAM CPC set to “Low Flow”. AMS reset it to “High Flow” then counts came up to 1000.
3. Camera Demist – when selected ON, interference seen on FFC i.e. flickering
4. SO – Possible 10 ppb offset between instrument and reading on HORACE (higher reading on HORACE).

Aircraft

1. Tested 28V Power supplies pre-flight for interference at the large radiometers. AMS appears to pick this up.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 7.2.07

Flight No: 8267

Pre-Flighter: JT

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	NOT COME OFF STANDBY
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	NOT RITED
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT RITED
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	NO
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	OPTICS TOO COLD !!
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	WORK DONE BY MO NO INSTRUCTIONS GIVEN
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	NOT RITED
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
Proceed to External Checks				
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>No.</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	GN
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<i>[Signature]</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		<i>[Signature]</i>
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
46	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		<i>[Signature]</i> ice in centre trap

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B267:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	On SID2 PC which is in Germany
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	15 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk